

APPLICATION OF GOOGLE TRANSLATE FOR WRITING THESIS ABSTRACT IN ENGLISH (GRAMMAR ERROR ANALYSIS)

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Abstract: *Google Translate is a popular translation and is used by most people around the world. Google Translate not only offers translation in various languages, it can even speed up work Translate. In learning the new norm, Google Translate is considered the easiest way to facilitate translation work and assist students in completing academic assignments. Based on the preliminary survey that had been done toward fifteen English thesis abstracts of post graduate students, it was found a lot of mistakes in the writing (tenses). This research aims at identifying the use of tenses/grammar in English thesis abstracts. The type of this research is descriptive through documentation study approach. The population was all English thesis abstracts at post graduate program Jakarta Islamic University. The sampling was purposive sampling. The data were analyzed descriptively. The results of the research showed that the inappropriate use of tense was more than that of the appropriate one in the part of background; the inappropriate use of tense was more than that of the appropriate one in the part of research method; the inappropriate use of tense was more than that of the appropriate one in the part of result (findings); the appropriate use of tense was more than that of the inappropriate one in the part of discussion; and the appropriate use of tense was more than that of the inappropriate one in the part of conclusion and suggestion*

Keywords: Abstract, Appropriate, Google Translate, Inappropriate, Tense, Use.

Abstrak: Google Translate merupakan terjemahan yang populer dan digunakan oleh sebagian besar orang di seluruh dunia. Google Translate tidak hanya menawarkan terjemahan dalam berbagai bahasa, bahkan dapat mempercepat pekerjaan penerjemahan. Dalam mempelajari norma baru, Google Translate dianggap sebagai cara termudah untuk memfasilitasi pekerjaan terjemahan dan membantu mahasiswa dalam menyelesaikan tugas akademik. Berdasarkan survey pendahuluan yang telah dilakukan terhadap lima belas abstrak tesis bahasa Inggris mahasiswa pascasarjana, ditemukan banyak kesalahan dalam penulisan (tenses). Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengidentifikasi penggunaan tenses/grammar dalam abstrak tesis bahasa Inggris. Jenis penelitian ini adalah deskriptif melalui pendekatan studi dokumentasi.

Populasinya adalah seluruh abstrak tesis bahasa Inggris pada program pascasarjana Universitas Islam Jakarta. Pengambilan sampel dilakukan secara purposive sampling. Data dianalisis secara deskriptif. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa penggunaan tense yang tidak tepat lebih banyak daripada penggunaan tense yang tepat pada bagian latar; penggunaan tense yang tidak tepat lebih banyak daripada penggunaan tense yang tepat dalam bagian metode penelitian; penggunaan tense yang tidak tepat lebih banyak daripada yang tepat pada bagian hasil (temuan); penggunaan tense yang tepat lebih banyak daripada penggunaan tense yang tidak tepat dalam bagian diskusi; dan

penggunaan tense yang tepat lebih banyak daripada yang tidak tepat di bagian kesimpulan dan saran

Kata kunci: Abstrak, Tepat, Google Translate, Kurang Tepat, Tense, Penggunaan.

INTRODUCTION

One of the obligations for students as graduation requirement is to write a paper scientific. Scientific writing is written work that arranged systematically according to the rules based on the results of scientific thinking. Work Scientific reports are divided into several types namely: reports research, papers, scientific papers, theses, dissertations and proposals (Jauhari, 2010). One of the important elements in scientific writing is abstract. This is because the abstract is summary results containing the essence of scientific work. Abstract is also a benchmark for the content of the scientific work. Readers will be interested or not to read scientific works is also determined by the abstract.

Abstract is placed on the first page of an article with the aim of helping readers quickly and definitely know the purpose, content of a study (Polontalo, 2013). Abstract is a brief description of a scientific paper that includes the background, the problem of the study, the method used, the results obtained, conclusions, and suggestions.

Abstract is made in two languages: Indonesian and English. Writing abstract in English is a response from where the progress of science and technology scientific works published via the internet so that scientific works can be accessed globally. Therefore, abstract translation from Indonesian to English is very crucial. Abstract writing in English version must be written with accordance to the rules of writing right English, in this case it must be written with the appropriate type of sentence (tenses). Many errors in writing sentences (tenses) in the introduction to the abstract. This is because most of the students translate abstract from Indonesian into English word by word by word. This is not in accordance with the rules in translate.

Translating is an act of transferring text from the source language into target language in a certain context (Foster, 2008). Translate is a process and method used to convey the meaning of the original language into the target language and more focused on the idea of meaning and good grammar (Ghazala, 2015).

Today's technology is growing. Technology is used in most aspects of life including in the field of teaching and learning. With the new situation that is sweeping the world, technology is seen as a very important and necessary aspect. However, there are times when the technology used does not necessarily guarantee the expected results and requires human intervention. It can be seen in the use of Google Translate. Google Translate has long been used since it was discovered by Google and was introduced in April 2006. Google Translate is a translation tool that is now widely used throughout the world by all groups, ages, backgrounds and

professions. Students in higher education institutions are no exception (Lubna Abd Rahman, & Arnida A. Bakar 2018).

University Students in Indonesia also use Google Translate as their translation tool to prepare academic assignments, including translating abstract thesis from Indonesian to English. This paper discusses the results of the grammar error analysis of post graduate students at Jakarta Islamic University in making English abstract in their thesis.

Based on the result of the study that had been done by Kusumawati dan Sugiarsi (2020) with the title “ Analisis Penulisan Abstrak Bahasa Inggris Pada Karya Tulis Ilmiah Mahasiswa D3 Rekam Medis Dan Informasi Kesehatan Stikes Mitra Husada Karanganyar” toward fifteen thesis English abstracts of education in 2019/2020, it was still found a lot of mistakes in the writing (tenses). This research aims at identifying the use of tenses in sentences applied in the English abstract of thesis. Based on this, it is necessary to implement research with the title "Application of Google Translate For Writing Thesis Abstract in English”.

The process of translating from one language to another using Google Translate indirectly makes it the most popular translation tool in the world. Likewise, the use of Google Translate as a translation tool by students who make their thesis abstracts in English is also considered the easiest and fastest way to solve it. Especially in a pandemic situation, Google Translate is considered a savior and helper they trust to ensure English abstracts can be prepared. However, does Google Translate really help students in preparing their assignments? When viewed from the point of view of the speed of time, it is undeniable that Google Translate can translate in the blink of an eye. If you look at the accuracy of the meaning, is Google Translate able to produce a translation that is truly correct or at least in accordance with the target culture and language? This is the problem

The academic literature uses abstracts to concisely communicate complex research. Abstract can act as a stand-alone entity, not a full paper. Thus, abstracts are used by many organizations as a basis for selecting proposed research for presentation in the form of posters, platform/oral presentations or workshop presentations at academic conferences. Most bibliographic databases index only abstracts rather than providing the entire text of the paper.

Abstracts can convey the main results and conclusions of a research such as theses, dissertations and scientific article. An abstract allows one to screen a large number of papers for ones where the researcher can be more confident that they will be relevant to his research. Once papers have been selected on the basis of abstracts, they should be read carefully to evaluate their relevance. It is generally agreed that one should not base reference citations on the abstract alone, but on the content of the entire paper.

According to the 2015 scientific paper writing guidelines, it states that the abstract is a brief description of the reasons for the research being

conducted, the method or approach chosen or used in research, important results, and the main conclusions from the results of scientific work writing activities, such as theses, theses, and dissertation.

In abstract writing, we must also understand the nature and elements of the abstract. In making abstracts, it has informative and descriptive properties. Informative and descriptive, meaning that the data or information contained in the abstract is based on existing data and facts. and it is not recommended to briefly include information that has no correct data and facts into the abstract.

Limitless communication and the use of social media today have made the world feel smaller and smaller. Regardless of location, country, or nation, communication now no longer requires a face-to-face meeting. Knowledge and information can also be searched more easily through cyberspace. However, the language problem still exists. In this case, the translation is still of interest (Kusumawati & Sugiarsi 2002).

Loutayf & Soledad (2017) stated that human translation is central to communication between culture and language. There are times when human translation is seen as time consuming and complicated. In this case, Google Translate is seen as the best solution and easy to achieve. Google Translate is a text translation that is done by a computer without involving humans. Google Translate is also known as fast translation which produces translations in very short time. Users only need to enter words, phrases, sentences, paragraphs and continue to be translated by the selected translation tool.

Doro (2013) Stated that one of the most popular translation tools is Google Translate. There are also many language options offered. Google Translate is not only used in communication but it is also used as a learning tool for most students.

Students who write abstract on their theses are no exception using Google Translate. English is one of several languages used in writing research abstracts. A translation tool is a translation provided by a computer, without human assistance or not. The use of this translation tool is very widespread because it does not need to be paid for and is easily accessible without calculating place and time.

Furthermore, this translation tool is capable of translating words, phrases and sentences without the need to refer to a dictionary. There are too many languages offered, more than 50 languages (Supatranonta & Pisamai, 2012). Using Google Translate as a translation tool can sometimes help with translation work. However, there are translations given that are not in accordance with the context and culture of the target language. The results of the translation using the translation tool are simply different when compared to the translation that is used done by humans. The same impression as in the source text is easier to understand through human translation.

Translators should not rely solely on translation tools. Terzi, Canan & Arslanturk, Yalcin. (2014) states that translation tools only speed up the

translation process, but the meaning is not necessarily correct. This is also supported by Zhen-ye & Ning. (2008). which states that the results of the translation process by Google Translate are still limited and have not provided the expected translation results. The quality of the translation from one language to another is not always the same.

Abstracts in the English version must be written in accordance with good English writing rules for abstracts in scientific writings. Sentences in the abstract must be written with the appropriate tenses.

Table 1. Tenses Guide Used in The Abstract

Type of Information	Tenses	Examples
Giving background details	Present tense	<i>The method <u>is</u> already well known for its efforts to improve the learning result</i> <i>The study <u>focused</u> on 2 main areas.</i>
Describing the research activity	Simple past tense, present perfect tense	<i>The framework for this error analysis <u>has been developed</u>.</i> <i>We <u>carried out</u> a series of field tests.</i>
Describing the methods	Simple past tense (active or passive)	<i>A large number of samples <u>were tested</u> for this study.</i> <i>Results <u>indicated</u> that the problem is even more serious than previously predicted</i>
Reporting results	Simple past tense	<i>The third model <u>proved</u> to be more durable than the other four.</i>
	Present tense verbs indicating tentativeness: is possible; is likely; appears; seems; might. Modal auxiliary verbs: can; may; could; might.	<i>This <u>indicates</u> that there are, in fact, several factors contributing to the decrease.</i> <i>It <u>appears</u> that the incidence of human error <u>cannot</u> be eliminated at any stage.</i> <i>There <u>might</u> be a need for revising the list of criteria within the next 5-10 years.</i>

Source: http://cc.oulu.fi/~smac/TRW/tense_abstract.htm

The result of the study that had been done by Nuraini Binti Ismail (2021) The google translate results showed errors such as mistranslation of names, errors of pronouns and grammar errors (tenses). Error in translation of the name. The word name is used to describe the name of something animate such as people, animals and inanimate things such as

places, objects and plants (Nik Safiah Karim, Farid Mohd Onn; Hashim bin Hj Musa; Abdul Hamid Mahmood; 2011).

Example 1

(SL = Source Language TL= Target Language)

SL: Selamat pagi Mery

TL: Good morning Merry

In Example 1, Google Translate has translated the word **Mery** (person's name) with the equivalent **Merry** (meaning to marry)

Pronoun translation error. Pronouns are words that replace words that refer to names: Johan = He, Dewi = She, Johan and Dewi = They

In Indonesian there are names of people that are commonly used for both types of men or women such as; Eri, Novi, Anis or Win, pronouns **He** for boy and **She** for girl.

Example 2

SL: Saya tinggal dirumah teman lelaki saya Anis waktu libur semester, rumahnya bagus sekali

TL: I stayed at my friend Anis's house when semester break, her house is very nice.

The sentence in Example 2 shows that there is an error in the use of personal pronouns. **Her house** as translated by Google Translate in terms of Anis in the sentence above shows a man not a woman. This example of translation can show that Google Translate does not care about the context of the meaning of words or expressions given by its users. In the original sentence, the gender of the person (male) is meant. It can clearly be shown through the name used, namely Anis. The word provided by Google Translate indicates female gender.

Example 3

SL: May : Kristina, apakah teman kamu Khadijah dan Ahmad telah membantu kamu?

Kristina: Iya, dia telah membantu saya selama dua minggu.

TL: May : Kristina, have your friends Khadijah and Ahmad been helping you?

Christina: Yes, he has been helping me for two weeks.

In this sentence also the personal pronouns Khadijah and Ahmad have been translated as **him** by Google Translate. This example also shows that Google Translate does not care about the meaning of context in providing equivalent words or expressions given by its users. The pronoun **he** in this sentence should be written as **they** because it denotes male and female gender.

Example 4

SL: Jony : Dimana rumah kamu?

Imran: **itu** terletak di seksion 7, Kota Wisata.

TL: Jony: Where is your house?

Imran : He is located in section 7, Kota Wisata

Also in Example 4, Google Translate has translated the pronoun it self as **him** into Indonesian. This is the wrong personal pronoun because house

in Indonesian is given the gender as male and woman. The pronoun should be used to refer to the house.

Grammar Errors (tenses)

The analysis also shows that there are grammatical errors in the tenses used.

Example 5

SL: Saya tidur larut malam tadi malam, sekitar jam 3.00 pagi
Biasanya saya tidur jam 9.00 malam

TL: I go to bed quite late last night, around 3.00 a.m.
I usually go to bed at 9.00 pm

Example 6

SL: Aisyah, Anda pergi kemana kemaren

TL: Aisyah: Where you go yesterday?

SI: Saya pergi ketaman kemaren

TL: Fifi: I go to the park yesterday.

Example 7

SL: Raja: Kapan Anda tiba?

TL: Raja: When you arrive?

SL: Farhana: Saya tiba tadi malam jam 6.00

TL: Farhana: I arrive at 6 o'clock in the evening,

Examples 5 to Example 7 showed sentences that contain errors in the Target Language. Grammar errors in the use of words that showed the past tense in Indonesian, the auxiliary word **did** is not needed. Bibard (2019) says that: To form the past participle using **did**, the past participle has to change the verb into verb 2. The sentences in these examples showed all the mistakes made involving the auxiliary **did**. Students proved not to add **did** to the auxiliary used for past questions and did not change the verb into verb 2 for statement sentences. This was an error because the past tense grammar rules in Indonesian do not require the additional word **did** for the question clause, nor do they require verb changes such as: **go-went** for irregular verbs and the addition of **ed** for regular verbs such as: **arrive - arrived**.

Before making an abstract, there are several things that must be considered, first make a general abstract standard. That is, each particular goal will have a requirement in making the abstract. For example, for the purpose of publishing an international seminar, the format or template will be slightly different depending on the organizer, as well as scientific journals. Therefore, here are some general provisions related to making an abstract: 1. The word count is about 250 words, 2. Choose British English or American English, must be consistent, 3. Consists of an introduction, research objectives, methods, results and discussion (if necessary), conclusions 4. Tenses:

Introduction = present tense

Research objective = past tense

method = past tense

result = past tense

Conclusion = present tense

Make an abstract with the standard format above, so we just need to refine it according to the requested format. The mistake that often occurs is using the Google Translate facility from the Indonesian to English version of the abstract without being refined again.

This paper is written based on the objective; (i) to find out the types of errors made by students when making a thesis abstract in English and (ii) to analyze the errors which was translated from Indonesian to English using Google Translate.

METHODOLOGY

This type of research design is observational with a descriptive approach. The point is data collection through observation of scientific paper documents with the aim of describing the suitability of abstract writing in English.

The population in this study were all abstracts in English on the thesis of postgraduate students at the Jakarta Islamic University. The sampling technique was purposive sampling and obtained a sample of 40 abstracts. Data collection is done through document study using a checklist. The data analysis in this study was descriptive, namely providing a description of the part consisting of the introduction, research objectives, methods, results and discussion (if necessary), conclusions. This qualitative research used two analyzes (i) text analysis. Text analysis was used by researchers to see the writings written by students who wrote research abstracts, (II) to find out the errors contained in the English sentences used.

RESULT

This research in particular can help students in writing English abstracts. Sentence examples can be used to show students' mistakes. The results of the analysis can also be shown to students so that they are careful when using Google Translate. Students also need to be reminded to pay attention to their writing results, especially after using Google Translate.

This research is limited to the writing of English abstracts written by students in their thesis. This research only involves error analysis of English abstracts. This research was conducted from January 2021 to July 2021. Only abstracts containing sentences in English were analyzed. Abstracts that were not written in English were not analyzed. Every English sentence is translated with Google Translate, looking at the translation, it was found that there were tenses which translations did not appropriate to English writing rules for abstracts in scientific writings.

Table 1. Analysis of the Use of Tenses in the Abstract of Students' English Thesis

Component	Appropriate n(%)	Inappropriate n(%)
Giving background details	19 (47,5%)	21 (52,5%)
Describing the research activity	17 (42,5%)	23 (57,5%)
Describing the methods	16 (40%)	24 (60%)
Reporting results	18 (45%)	22 (55%)
Stating conclusions	25 (62,5%)	15 (37,5%)
N (sample)	40	

Table 1 showed that the highest use of inappropriate tenses was found in the components of the research method as many as 24 (60%) abstracts in research articles. The error lies in the use of the Present Tense. The next highest error in using tenses was in the abstract background; namely the use of the Simple Present Tense test to refer to the preliminary survey that has been conducted; as much as 21 (52,5%). Errors in using Simple Present Tense tenses refer to Describing the research activity as many as 23 (57,5%). Likewise, errors in using tenses occur in writing research results; 22 (55%) namely the use of the Simple Present Tense. Most of the use of tenses in writing abstract conclusions is correct; 25 (62,5%) is the use of Simple Past Tense) . and which is not right; 15 (37,5%); Simple present tense.

DISCUSSION

Based on the description and analysis of the abstract data of the English thesis, it is obtained a description of the errors in the use of tenses contained in the introduction, research methods, results (findings), discussion, conclusions, and suggestions. The first finding in this study was the use of tenses in the introduction to an English abstract which included appropriate and Inappropriate. The use of the right tenses in the introduction was 19 (47,5%). The use of the right tenses in the introduction was to use the Simple Past Tense to explain what the researcher has done in his research.

The words *found* and *there were* refer to the Simple Past Tense which is used to express an event that has been done before (past). Meanwhile, there are 16 abstracts (53.3%) whose use of tenses is not appropriate, namely by using the Simple Present Tense to refer to in the preliminary survey that has been carried out: The word *shows* the Simple Present Tense which refers to on survey activities that have been carried out by researcher. The use of *shows* in this sentence is not appropriate because the survey was conducted by the researcher at a time before the research was conducted, so the correct word to replace *shows* is *showed*, which is the past tense (Verb 2) of show. The Simple Present Tense used

in the introduction is only limited to showing the facts and truth of the information we receive and is still relevant today and is considered correct,

The second finding in this study was the use of tenses in the research method section. The use of the right tenses found as many as 16 abstracts (40%). The appropriate tenses in the research method section were the Simple Past Tense, such as: "The population in this study were the whole new students at ..." and

"The instruments used a checklist and guidelines of unstructured interview". The words were and used show the Simple Past Tense where were is to be Past Tense while used is the past tense (Verb 2) of the word use, which means use. The were and used are appropriate because the Past Tense form in the method section in the abstract explains what the researcher has done related to the research approach that is implemented. There were also 24 abstracts (60%) with tenses is not appropriate, such as: "This study uses a cross-sectional approach." And "The instrument in this research is a questionnaire". The sentence shows the activities carried out by the researcher including the research approach carried out, so the use of uses and is (Present Tense) are not appropriate. The sentence should use the Simple Past Tense so that the correct sentence is: "This study used a cross-sectional approach." and "The instrument in this research was questionnaire". The use of the Simple Present Tense in the research methods section is only limited showing standard procedures and activities in research.

The third finding is the use of tenses in the results section. The use of the right tenses found as many as 18 abstracts (45%). Meanwhile, there are 22 (55%) abstracts (55%) with the use of the wrong tense, namely by using the Simple Present Tense to state the findings: "The result showed that"

The use of the word showed in the sentence is right because showed is a form past (Verb 2) which comes from the root word (Verb 1) show which means to show.

Meanwhile, there are 22 abstracts (55%)

with the use of the wrong tense, namely by using the Simple Present Tense for stated the findings: "The result of research shows that the world wall picture has been" and "The result of research shows that social class and cost of living still below standard ..."; and "The result of research shows that most of students' knowledge on teaching method is ...".

In all three sentences above there is the word shows which shows the use the Simple Present Tense in the results section findings. The word shows in that context is not appropriate because it refers to an outcome of an activity that has been done in the past. The word show should be written as showed (Simple Past Tense) which refers to past activities, so that the sentence becomes: "The result of research showed that the world wall picture has be "The result of research showed that social class and cost of living

still below standard ...”; and “The result of research showed that most of students’ knowledge on teaching method is ...”.

The fifth finding was the use of tense in the conclusions and suggestions section. There were 18 abstracts where the writer did not include conclusions and suggestions. The use of the right tense in the conclusions and suggestions section were 25 abstracts (62,5%). Meanwhile, there were 15 (37,5%) abstracts that the use of the tense was not correct, such as : “The conclusion of the study is that the management of risk in the university had not been carried out....” and “The suggestion in this study is that it was better to conduct socialization or training to” The use *is* (Simple Present Tense) at the conclusion an abstract is appropriate because it refers to gist, summary and implications of the findings. Whereas the use of *is* (Simple Present Tense) in the suggestion is also appropriate because to state something common, which in fact can implemented or not.

The outcomes of this analysis are close to the research conducted by Erna Adita Kusumawati dan Sri Sugiarsi in their research entitled “Analisis Penulisan Abstrak Bahasa Inggris Pada Karya Tulis Ilmiah Mahasiswa D3 Rekam Medis Dan Informasi Kesehatan Stikes Mitra Husada Karanganyar” the study concluded that the use of tenses the highest imprecision is found in the component research methods as many as 19 (63.3%) abstracts on research articles. The error lies in use of Present Tense. The next highest tense use error is in the introduction to the abstract; i.e. use tenses Simple Present Tense to refer to preliminary survey that has been conducted; as much 16(53,3%). Similarly, misuse thesis occurs in the writing of research results; that is use of Simple Present Tense. Most of the the use of tenses in writing abstract conclusions is correct; 20(66.6%) is the use of Simple Past tense) . and which is not right; 10(33.3%); Simple Present tense.

CONCLUSION

This research showed that there were inaccuracies and errors in the writing a thesis abstract in English, if Google Translate was used as a translation tool. The accuracy of meaning based on context and grammar was not noticed by this translation tool. To overcome this problem, students should understand the use of correct English grammar. If students still want to use Google Translate, they need to pay attention to the accuracy of the translation they get.

Based on the data exposure and research findings, several conclusions can be made. Errors in the use of tense in English abstracts in scientific writings (thesis) students of Master of Islamic Religious Education Postgraduate at the Islamic University of Jakarta, consist of the use of appropriate and inappropriate tenses. The use of inappropriate tenses is done more than the use of appropriate tenses, namely in the introduction, research methods, and research results (findings). While the

use of the right tense is found in the section discussion as well as conclusions and suggestions.

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